

Resilience of Underground Transportation Infrastructure in Coastal Regions: A Case Study

**Edwin Martinez¹, Jose Hernandez², Tonatiuh Rodriguez-Nikl, Ph.D.³, and Mehran Mazari,
Ph.D.⁴**

¹California State University Los Angeles, Department of Civil Engineering, 5151 University Drive, Los Angeles, CA 90032; e-mail: emarti95@calstatela.edu

²California State University Los Angeles, Department of Civil Engineering, 5151 University Drive, Los Angeles, CA 90032; e-mail: jhern387@calstatela.edu

³California State University Los Angeles, Department of Civil Engineering, 5151 University Drive, Los Angeles, CA 90032; e-mail: trodri7@calstatela.edu

⁴California State University Los Angeles, Department of Civil Engineering, 5151 University Drive, Los Angeles, CA 90032; e-mail: mmazari2@calstatela.edu

ABSTRACT

Infrastructure in coastal areas is vulnerable to extreme weather events such as storms, high tides, flooding and severe precipitation. These could drastically affect transportation infrastructure, including underground structures, which would result in greater construction, maintenance, and rehabilitation costs. Global climate change, especially increased precipitation, increased temperature, and sea level rise will further exacerbate the problem. Of these risks, sea level rise is the most important for coastal regions in the long-term. The projections of sea level rise for the next eighty years show a range of 0.8 ft. to 6.5 ft. Furthermore, the risk of sea level rise coupled with storm surge will increase the vulnerability of coastal transportation infrastructure including bridges, roads, tunnels, ports, and harbors. This paper reports on an assessment of the resilience of a representative set of underground transportation assets to extreme stressors in coastal regions. Sea level rise and storm surge scenarios were evaluated and the condition of underground transportation systems was assessed in each scenario using a vulnerability assessment tool.

INTRODUCTION

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), vulnerability is defined as the level at which the system or infrastructure component is exposed to the adverse effects of climate change and extreme weather events. Based on the definition of the system, other factors including environmental conditions, exposure to the weather stressors and distribution of the infrastructure components in the network, may also contribute to the vulnerability of the system (IPCC, 2007). In the context of transportation infrastructure, vulnerability is defined as the

susceptibility to damage and loss of structural integrity during or after the weather events. The factors affecting the vulnerability of the infrastructure systems include age, design criteria, exposure level, service conditions, and structural integrity. A disruption in one component of the infrastructure at a local scale may affect the regional network based on the proximity of the connected assets and level of service. These factors are prominent for underground transportation infrastructure the transit and transportation network. Exposure of these assets to extreme weather events in coastal areas, such as flash floods, storms, and hurricanes, may disrupt the local and regional transportation network (Larsen et al., 2007; Kirshen et al., 2006).

Although the effects of extreme weather events on transportation infrastructure are well understood, few studies have been dedicated to evaluating and investigating these effects. Furthermore, the evaluation of post-event condition of roadways and flooded infrastructure have been limited to few recent studies such as hurricane Katrina in Louisiana (Chen and Zhang, 2011) and Hurricane Sandy in New York and New Jersey (Kaufman et al, 2012).

The Federal Highway Administration published the “Climate Change & Extreme Weather Vulnerability Assessment Framework” as a guideline for transportation agencies to assess the vulnerability of their transportation infrastructure to extreme weather events and climate change (FHWA, 2012). The framework helps the state highway agencies and departments of transportation define their objectives and scopes, assess their transportation infrastructure vulnerability, and implement the results into a decision-making process. In the context of the framework, the resilience of transportation infrastructure is the function of exposure, adaptability, and sensitivity.

There are three steps to developing a vulnerability assessment framework: 1) assess current vulnerability, 2) estimate future conditions, and 3) estimate future vulnerabilities. The first component of this framework evaluates the vulnerability of the infrastructure to current stressors. The response of the system to the existing stressors may be extracted from the historical databases. The second step involves predicting the future impacts and weather events in the context of climate change, storm return periods, and extreme events with less predictability potential such as earthquakes. In evaluating the second step, a period of study, as well as dependability of prediction models based on the climate change trends influence the estimation of the future conditions.

METHODOLOGY

This paper reports on a preliminary assessment of a sample of underground subway stations in New York, using the Climate Change & Extreme Weather Vulnerability Assessment and Scoring Tool (VAST) proposed by the Federal Highway Administration (FHWA 2012). The assets were assessed under sea level rise and storm surge. The goals of the preliminary assessment are to provide an example for the application of the framework and to evaluate the applicability of the framework to underground transportation assets. This work is related to a previous study by some of the authors on the effects of sea level rise on roads in coastal Los Angeles (Valenzuela et al. 2017).

Study Area

Figure 1 shows the location of New York City subway stations in low-lying coastal zones. Many of these stations are susceptible to the intrusion of flood and stormwater during the extreme weather events. Studying the vulnerability of these assets in the response to the environmental stressors in the VAST model will be helpful in understanding the resilience of underground transportation infrastructures within the study area.

Figure 1 – Study area and location of underground subway stations

Prediction of Sea Level Rise and Storm Surge

In this study, the resilience of selected transportation infrastructure facilities was evaluated with the following sea level rise (SLR) and storm surge (SS) data. The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) has provided a visualization tool that estimates the flood exposure in coastal regions due to shallow coastal flooding, storm surge (SS), and sea level rise (NOAA 2017a). NOAA also provides a sea level rise (SLR) viewer (NOAA 2017b) and a tool to view the National Storm Surge Hazard Maps (NOAA 2107c). Figure 2 shows the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) flood zones; Figure 3 illustrates the modeled storm surge inundation depths, and Figure 4 shows the prediction of different Sea Level Rise (SLR) scenarios above the current Mean Higher High Water (MHHW).

Figure 2 – FEMA flood zones (red is high risk, 1% annual chance; orange is moderate risk, 0.2% annual chance)

Figure 3 – Storm surge inundation depth, Category 1 (left) and Category 4 (right); less than 3 ft (blue), 3-6 ft (yellow), 6-9 ft (orange), greater than 9 ft (red)

Figure 4 – Sea level rise (SLR) scenario for 2 ft (left) and 6 ft (right) above current Mean Higher High Water

VULNERABILITY ASSESSMENT ANALYSIS

The following sections discuss the process of building different scenarios and assess the vulnerability of selected underground transportation infrastructures within the study area using the FHWA's Vulnerability Assessment Scoring Tool (VAST). Each section below represents a component of the model. The tool, in the form of an Excel spreadsheet, is available for download from the FHWA (2017).

Stressors

A climate stressor, as defined by VAST, is an external change in climate that may cause damage to the transportation system. The New York Subway system has had previous experience with the flooding of their stations. As the New York subway system is located near coastal regions, it has been subjected to both extreme weather conditions and climate change. This leaves the transportation system vulnerable to both sea level rise and storm surge flooding.

Assets

The asset type selected in the spreadsheet was "tunnels". The asset type in VAST guides the choices the user makes in populating the model. The following three representative stations were chosen with varying degrees of vulnerability based on an initial inspection the above-mentioned maps: South Ferry, Spring Street, and Canal Street. For storm surge, each asset was modeled twice to simulate stations with and without flood protection.

Exposure Indicators

VAST provides an exposure indicator library that can be browsed for each climate stressor. The exposure indicators used in this study came from these suggestions. The exposure indicator used for SLR was inundation depth. The score for inundation depth was calculated by subtracting station elevation from sea level rise. Negative values of inundation depth, which represent an asset above water, were represented in the model with a score of zero. Elevations were taken from publically available maps.

Two indicators were used for storm surge (SS): modeled surge inundation depth and presence in the FEMA coastal flood zone. Estimation was required with storm surge depth because of the coarse resolution of the map. The storm surge score used in the model was the modeled SS inundation depth plus the expected sea level rise. This assumes that the storm surge depth is above the MHHW at the time of the scenario.

Two scenarios for climate stressors were defined. Scenario 1 represents low severity with a category 1 storm and SLR of 2 feet. Scenario 2 represents high severity with a category 4 storm and SLR of 6 feet. A category 4 storm was chosen because category 5 was insufficiently mapped. Tables 1 and 2 detail the station elevations, sea level rise, and inundation depth.

Table 1 - High SLR Inundation Depth

Asset (Subway Station)	Existing Elevation	Sea Level Rise (High 6ft)	Inundation Depth SLR – Existing Elevation
South Ferry	4 ft.	6 ft.	2 ft.
Spring Street	24 ft.	6 ft.	-18 ft.
Canal Street	18 ft.	6 ft.	-12 ft.

Table 2 - Low SLR Inundation Depth

Asset (Subway Station)	Existing Elevation	Sea Level Rise (Low 2ft)	Inundation Depth SLR – Existing Elevation
South Ferry	4 ft.	2 ft.	-2 ft.
Spring Street	24 ft.	2 ft.	-22 ft.
Canal Street	18 ft.	2 ft.	-16 ft.

Sensitivity and Adaptive Capacity Indicators

The indicator library did not provide suggestions for either sensitivity or adaptive capacity under the tunnel category despite allowing tunnels as an asset class. The libraries for roads, transit assets, and rail lines were used instead to generate possible indicators for use in this study. Some interesting research developments are on the horizon for flood protection, e.g. the Resilient Tunnel Project from the Department of Homeland Security (DHS 2014). Thus, flood protection was used as an indicator of sensitivity to storm surge. Two assumed levels of flood protection were considered for each asset: unprotected (100% water intrusion) and protected but not perfect (20% water intrusion); greater water intrusion indicates greater sensitivity. Headway, indicative of the traffic in each station, was used as a measure to indicate the sensitivity to both sea level rise and storm surge. The reasoning is that the community response is more sensitive to an asset that is depended upon by a greater number of people; greater headway indicates greater sensitivity. Headway was found through Metropolitan Transportation Authority (MTA) subway schedules. When calculating the headway of the stations without a schedule, the closest station with a schedule was used as a reference to calculate the headway. Because of the preliminary nature of this analysis and the lack of information about appropriate adaptive capacity indicators, it was decided not to consider adaptive capacity at this time.

Results

Tables 3 and 4 summarize the resulting vulnerability scores for scenarios 1 and 2, respectively. Figure 5 summarizes the number of assets in each vulnerability range (not exposed, low, moderate, and high). Scores are from zero (least vulnerable) to four (most vulnerable). The scores are relative scores for each stressor. These results illustrate how VAST assigns a single metric for vulnerability to aid decision-makers in allocating limited resources. For instance, the results indicate that South Ferry has increased vulnerability between Scenario 1 and Scenario 2 in the SLR case and that all stations have increased vulnerability in the storm surge case. The results also indicate different ranking in the SLR and SS case. This is because SLR is a slow process that depends solely on elevation and hydrologic connectivity to the ocean, while SS is a transient

process that also depends on the exposure of the site to the direction of the storm surge. Lastly, the results indicate the relative benefit of installing flood protection at the various sites. For example in the Storm Surge case for Scenario 2, South Ferry’s score improved by 0.9 with flood protection while Spring Street’s score improved only 0.4.

Table 3 - Most vulnerable assets to each stressor in Scenario 1 sorted by score (from VAST model)

Sea Level Rise			Storm Surge		
ID	Name	Score	ID	Name	Score
SF	South Ferry	1.7	SF	South Ferry	1.8
CS	Canal Street	1.7	SS	Spring Street	1.7
SS	Spring Street	0.7	CS	Canal Street	1.5
			SS FP	Spring Street Flood protection	1.3
			SF FP	South Ferry Flood Protection	1.0
			CS FP	Canal Street Flood protection	1.0

Table 4 - Most vulnerable assets to each stressor in Scenario 2 sorted by score (from VAST model)

Sea Level Rise			Storm Surge		
ID	Name	Score	ID	Name	Score
SF	South Ferry	2.7	SF	South Ferry	2.2
CS	Canal Street	1.7	CS	Canal Street	1.8
SS	Spring Street	0.7	SS	Spring Street	1.7
			SF FP	South Ferry Flood Protection	1.3
			SS FP	Spring Street Flood protection	1.3
			CS FP	Canal Street Flood protection	1.3

Figure 5 – Vulnerability assessment of assets within the study area (from VAST model)

SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

The Vulnerability Assessment Scoring Tool is a powerful program used to assess the components of a transportation system. In this the paper, the tool was used to evaluate a representative subset of New York subway system to show how the tool is used and to determine how well it applies to underground assets. Three stations were evaluated to assess the vulnerability to storm surge and sea level rise. The results in the previous section show how the tool can be used for decision-making. With regard to the tool's applicability to underground assets, we noted that although the tool lists tunnels as an asset class, it does not provide any information about appropriate indicators to use for the sensitivity and adaptive capacity of such assets. Adding this information to the model would help users select the most appropriate indicators rather than having to use the indicators used for other asset classes, which may not be applicable.

This study was preliminary in nature, so there are several aspects that were intentionally simplified and would be of interest in follow-up studies. First, we determined that soil parameters would be an important vulnerability indicator for underground infrastructure because water intrusion is an important factor in the durability of underground infrastructure components. However, we did not include it in the model because it was not clear, without detailed boring logs, how to generate meaningful values for use in VAST. Additional research is needed to determine how to best incorporate this indicator in the model. Second, we considered the stations as isolated assets when in fact they are tightly connected; if one station is compromised, flooding of the tunnel system may affect functionality at and between several stations. A more comprehensive study would consider how the vulnerability of individual stations affects the entire network of linked tunnels and stations. Lastly, we did not consider adaptive capacity because of the absence of guidance in the framework. Further research in this area is warranted.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Support from the University Transportation Center for Underground Transportation Infrastructure (UTC-UTI) at the Colorado School of Mines for funding this research under Grant No. 69A3551747118 from the U.S. Department of Transportation (DOT) is gratefully acknowledged. The contents of this report reflect the views of the authors, who are responsible for the facts and the accuracy of the information presented herein. This document is disseminated in the interest of information exchange. The report is funded, partially or entirely, by a grant from the U.S.

Department of Transportation's University Transportation Centers Program. However, the U.S. Government assumes no liability for the contents or use thereof.

REFERENCES

- Chen, X., and Zhang, Z. (2014), "Effects of Hurricanes Katrina and Rita flooding on Louisiana pavement performance," *Pavement Materials, Structures, and Performance*, ASCE, pp. 212-221.
- DHS (2014). "Resilient Tunnel Project" brochure. https://www.dhs.gov/sites/default/files/publications/Resilient%20Tunnel%20Project-508_0.pdf, accessed 11/2017.
- FHWA (2012). "Climate change and extreme weather vulnerability assessment framework," Federal Highway Administration (FHWA), U.S. Department of Transportation.
- FHWA (2017). "Tools – Climate Change Adaptation", <https://www.fhwa.dot.gov/environment/sustainability/resilience/tools/>, accessed 11/2017.
- ICF, (2008). "Potential Impacts of Global Sea Level Rise on Transportation Infrastructure," prepared by ICF International for U.S. DOT Center for Climate Change and Environmental Forecasting.
- Kaufman, S., Qing, C., Levenson, N., and Hanson, M. (2012). "Transportation During and After Hurricane Sandy," Rudin Center for Transportation NYU Wagner Graduate School of Public Service, pp. 1–36.
- Kirshen, P., Ruth, M., & Anderson, W. (2006). *Climate's long-term impacts on urban infrastructures and services: the case of Metro Boston* (pp. 190-252). Edward Elgar Publishers, Cheltenham.
- Larsen, E. W., Girvetz, E. H., & Fremier, A. K. (2007). Landscape level planning in alluvial riparian floodplain ecosystems: using geomorphic modeling to avoid conflicts between human infrastructure and habitat conservation. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 79(3), 338-346.
- NOAA (2017a). "Coastal Flood Exposure Map", <https://coast.noaa.gov/floodexposure/#/map>, accessed 11/2017.
- NOAA (2017b). "Sea Level Rise Viewer", <https://coast.noaa.gov/slr/#/layer/slr>, accessed 11/2017.
- NOAA (2017c). "Sea Level Rise Viewer", <http://noaa.maps.arcgis.com/apps/MapSeries/index.html?appid=d9ed7904dbec441a9c4dd7b277935fad>, accessed 11/2017.
- Valenzuela, Y., Rosas, R., Mazari, M., Risse, M., and Rodriguez-Nikl, T. (2017). "Resilience of Road Infrastructure in Response to Extreme Weather Events", *International Conference on Sustainable Infrastructure*, ASCE.